

GAYATRI MANTRA CHANTING ON FORCED VITAL CAPACITY (FVC)

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INTRODUCTION

The present study is innovative and important, because in COVID-19 Pandemic it was observed that people those had poor lungs ability affected by Corona Virus. GO's and NGO's reported that, due to the pollution, number of people suffering from shortness of breath, Cognitive Dysfunction, Fatigue, Anxiety, Depression, Muscle Aches, Loss of Smell etc. All these are the burning and measure health issue of the people living in Metropolitan Cities.

During the review of related literature, it was found that very few literatures on the study of effect of the Gayatri Mantra was found. Out of them, very few related literature reveals that Mantra Meditation is effective in improving pulmonary function. Hence, the study entitled 'Gayatri Mantra Chanting on Forced Vital Capacity' was planned to examine the output of the related literature and to study the effect of the Gayatri Mantra Chanting Program on Pulmonary Function with the aim of filling the gap in research in the particular area of health and fitness through manipulating Spiritual Mantra Technique by using the following methodology.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF THE TERM USED

- **Gayatri Mantra**

The Gayatri Mantra is a chanting of 'Om bhur bhuvahsvah, tatsavitur varenyam, bhargo devasya dhimahi, dhiyo yonah prachodayat'.

- **Forced Vital capacity (FVC)**

Forced Vital capacity (FVC) is the maximum amount of air a person can expel from the lungs after a maximum inhalation.

METHODOLOGY THE STUDY

To conduct the study, twenty (n=20) housewives aged 40–50 years from Sahkar Nagar, Wadala, Mumbai were served as a sample. The probable sampling method was used to select the samples from the population and then again, selected subjects were divided randomly into control and experimental groups. The experimental group received daily 30-minute Gayatri Mantra Chanting Program for one month, whereas the control group did not receive a Gayatri Mantra Chanting Program. Both the groups were tested before and after the treatment. Collected data was analysed by using standard statistics technology, One Way ANOVA, to test the stated null hypothesis.

RESULT ON FORCED VITAL CAPACITY (FVC)

Table No.1 Shows N, Mean Score and standard Deviation of Forced Vital Capacity of Pre-Test, Post-Test of Control Group, and Experimental Groups.

			N	Mean Score	Std. Deviation
Forced Vital Capacity Pre	Control Group		10	2.21	0.46
	Experimental Group		10	2.32	0.30
Forced Vital Capacity Post	Control Group		10	1.92	0.45
	Experimental Group		10	2.44	0.30

Table No. 1 shows that the mean score of the pre-tests of the Control Group is 2.21 and SD is 0.46 and the mean score of pre-tests of the Experimental Group is 2.32 and SD is 0.30, whereas as in the case of the post-tests Mean sore Control Group is 1.92 and SD is 0.45 and the mean score of Experimental Group is 2.44 and SD is 0.30. A graphic presentation of the same has been presented in figure No. 1.

Table No. 2: - Sum of Squares, ‘df’ Mean Square, ‘F’ Ratio of Forced Vital Capacity of Between Group, Within Group of Control and Experimental Groups.

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Forced Vital Capacity Pre	Between Groups	0.061	1	0.061	0.416	.527	$p \geq 0.05$
	Within Groups	2.617	18	0.145			
Forced Vital Capacity Post	Between Groups	1.394	1	1.394	6.624	.019	$P \leq 0.05$
	Within Groups	3.780	18	0.210			

It can be seen in table No. 2, the value of the Sum of Squares of Pre-Test of Forced Vital Capacity between the Groups is 0.061 with df 1, the value of Mean Square is also 0.061 and the 'F' value is 0.416, which is not significant. It means the mean value of pre-tests of control and experimental groups are more or less similar to each other. In case of Post Test Forced Vital Capacity between the Groups, the value of the Sum of Squares is 1.394 with the 'df' 1, the value of Mean Square is also 1.394 and the 'F' value is 6.64, which is significant. It indicates that the mean scores of the post-test of control and experimental groups differ significantly from each other.

INFLUENCE OF GAYATRI MANTRA ON FORCED VITAL CAPACITY (FVC)

As the result obtained from one way ANOVA presented in Table No.1 shows that the Mean score of pre-tests of Forced Vital Capacity of Control Group and Experimental groups are serially 2.21 and 2.32 which is statistically not significant, but in case of post-tests Mean scores of Forced Vital Capacity of Control and Experimental Group are 1.92 and **2.44** which is significant. It indicates that the mean scores of the post-test of control and experimental groups differ significantly from each other. Mean score of post-tests of Forced Vital Capacity of Experimental Group is increased by 0.52 liter. Therefore, it can be stated that Gayatri Mantra Chanting is effective in improving Forced Vital Capacity and the stated null hypothesis i.e. *'There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Forced Vital Capacity of post-test of control and the experimental group is rejected.* To support to the obtained result reviews of related literature are presented below.

(Ni Luh Putu Thrisna Dewi, Muhamad Thohar Arifin, & Suhartini Ismail, 2020) Studied the Influence of Gayatri Mantra and Emotional Freedom Technique on Quality of Life of Post-Stroke Patients, the conclusion of this study was Gayatri Mantra and Emotional Freedom Technique were significantly effective on quality of life of post-stroke patients.

(Ruchi Dua, et al., 2023) Conducted an exploratory randomized controlled trial on COVID-19 Patients to study the role of Yoga, in this study patients performed a one-hour yoga session that included Pranayama and Gayatri Mantra chant for 14 days. The results of the study was, incorporating pranayama and Gayatri Mantra chant practices in hospitalized patients with moderate COVID-19 pneumonia was showed a notable reduction in high-sensitivity c-reactive protein levels and fatigue severity scale scores in the Intervention Group.

(Ampere A. Tseng, 2022) Conducted a study entitled ‘Scientific Evidence of Health Benefits by Practicing Mantra Meditation: Narrative Review’. The review discovers evidence that Mantra Meditation can provide various degrees of beneficial effects on the four areas considered, studies with larger participants, superior quality, and a few others.

CONCLUSION THE STUDY

This experiment warrants the following **Conclusion**:

- Four weeks Gayatri Mantra Chanting training program helps to improve Forced Vital Capacity of housewives of aged 40-50 years.

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